

THE THERMAL SPIKE BEHAVIOUR OF CARBON FIBRE
REINFORCED PLASTICS

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UKABSTRACT

Carbon fibre reinforced plastics absorb moisture from the service environment. The influence of applied tensile loads on the moisture absorption of composites has been modelled in terms of changes in the matrix free volume. A model has been developed for the case of ($\pm 45^\circ$) laminates. The changes produced in the moisture absorption characteristics of three angle plied laminates as a result of applying a series of rapid excursions to 135°C , have also been studied. The resultant fall in high temperature mechanical properties is discussed in terms of microscopic evidence for fibre matrix debonding and inter-laminar cracking. It is suggested that cooling from 135°C produces the damage.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP's) are being recommended for use in the outer skins of supersonic military aircraft. The skins experience rapid heating, by air friction, to temperatures of about 135°C as a result of acceleration to supersonic speeds. This process is known as thermal spiking.

Collings et al [1] showed that under certain conditions, laminates which already contain considerable moisture undergo more rapid moisture absorption after thermal spiking. The equilibrium moisture absorption is also increased, and in certain cases matrix cracking occurs. The present work provides further evidence of the extent to which moisture absorption rates are increased by spiking, and compares the behaviour of

three materials in this respect. Laminate A was a $\pm 45^\circ$ carbon reinforced epoxy material which prior to hygrothermal exposure had a high glass transition temperature (T_g), laminate B was similar, but based on a tougher epoxy system with a lower T_g , and laminate C was carbon fibre reinforced PEEK (polyether-ether ketone), for which the T_g was intermediate but the matrix was much tougher, but less hydrophilic. The fibre volume fractions (V_f) were as follows: A, 0.60; B, 0.57; C, 0.61.

Stress Effects on Diffusion

It was also hoped that evidence could be provided about the effect of an applied tensile stress on the post-spiking behaviour. Broutman and Gillat [2] found that a tensile stress σ could increase the rate of diffusion and also the value of the equilibrium moisture absorption M_M . They attributed these effects to matrix cracking and interfacial damage. Marom and Neumann [3] developed a model for moisture diffusion into stressed unidirectional laminates, according to which the ratio D_σ/D_0 is greater than unity for tensile loads, except when the fibre axis is at a very small angle to the principal stress axis. The model assumes that the diffusion process depends on the free volume of the matrix (since carbon fibres absorb virtually no water) and predicts the volume strain of the matrix $(\Delta V/V_0)_m$ as a function of stress and the loading angle.

If we assume that all the plies are orthogonal, we can simplify Marom and Neumann's expression to apply to $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates and obtain an expression:

$$\left(\frac{\Delta V}{V_0}\right)_m = \sigma \left[\frac{1}{E_L} (\cos^4\theta + \sin^4\theta + \frac{\sin^2 2\theta}{2} - 2\gamma_{LT}) - \frac{1}{E_F} \left(\frac{E_F \cos^2\theta}{E_L} + \sin^2\theta (1 - 2\gamma_F) \right) \right] \dots (1)$$

where E_F = Young's modulus of the fibres

E_L = Young's modulus of a (0,90)s laminate

γ_F = Poisson's ratio of the fibres

γ_{LT} = Poisson's ratio of the composite in the plane defined by lines parallel and normal to the fibre axis within the plane of each lamina. The value of the volume strain obtained is then substituted into an equation based on the Doolittle equation of state^[3], to give

D_σ/D_0 :

$$\ln\left(\frac{D_\sigma}{D_0}\right) = b \left[\frac{1}{V_{f0}} - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{\Delta V}{V_0}\right)_m + V_{f0}} \right] \dots (2)$$

where b = a constant which in this case is taken to be 1.

Following Fahmy and Hurt [4] we can take the fractional free volume, V_{f0} , to be 0.025. Thus the additional stress-induced moisture uptake can be predicted, and the consequences of subsequent spikes assessed in stressed as well as unstressed laminates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thermal Spiking

Pre-dried parallel-sided strip specimens (2 mm thick) were exposed to a 72°C, 96% R.H. environment until saturation was almost achieved. At one week intervals, over a period of 44 weeks, the specimens were removed, cooled to room temperature and weighed. Half the samples were thermally spiked to 135°C over a heating period of 5 minutes in a special oven of high thermal capacity, and maintained at 135°C for five minutes. They were then removed, cooled with a fan, and weighed prior to reintroduction into the hot/wet environment. Another set of specimens were similarly spiked over an eleven week period. Two of these were left at 135°C for 1.5 hours. After the spikes the specimens were left in the hot/wet environment to ensure that equilibrium moisture content was reached. The specimens were removed and a small section used for microscopical study. The remainder was tensile tested at high temperature. Specimens for scanning electron microscopy were cut at 45° to the edge of the sample and also across the width. These edges were polished to a three micron finish.

Exposure Under Load

Specimens of material A were loaded in constant strain jigs to one of three strains estimated to correlate with 20, 40 or 60% of the ultimate tensile failure stress. Because of stress relaxation, a repeated reloading procedure was used before introducing the jigs and runners into a 50°C, 96% R.H. environment. Load cells were fitted to several of these jigs to monitor the stress in representative specimens. After exposure the specimens were removed from the jigs and a 20 mm section removed from the gauge length for slicing in a microtome. Slices were weighed and then dried. A moisture profile of each sample was constructed from these data, and an overall moisture content calculated.

In addition some specimens were loaded to 60% of the ultimate tensile strength and after 20 days in the humidity cabinet, the still stressed specimens and the zero-load runners were removed for one 135°C spike. They were then returned to the cabinet for fifteen days. A section from each was removed for slicing and drying, and the remainder tensile tested at 130°C. A tensile jig, sufficiently small to fit into the chamber of a scanning electron microscope, was used to obtain photomicrographs of the edges of specimens under various loads.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The theory outlined above predicts that measurable increases in the diffusion coefficients can be attributed to stress effects without postulating physical damage mechanisms (see Table 1).

Despite a large number of approximations being made during the derivation of equation (1) a good correlation was found with the measured values of D_{σ}/D_0 . The assumption is made that the material responds linearly for all applied stresses. At the higher stress levels this is far from the truth, and the volume strain of the matrix will be higher than that predicted. This could explain the higher measured value of D_{σ}/D_0 at 150 MPa without the need to invoke physical damage mechanisms.

TABLE 1
Ratios of Diffusion Coefficients for $[(\pm 45^{\circ})_4]_S$ laminate of material A subjected to several tensile stresses

APPLIED STRESS (MPa)	PREDICTED RATIO D_{σ}/D_0 *	MEASURED RATIO D_{σ}/D_0
50	1.10	1.0
100	1.20	1.2
150	1.32	1.5

* D_{σ}/D_0 is the ratio of the diffusion coefficients of stressed and unstressed laminates respectively.

Table 2 shows the effect of absorbed moisture on the high temperature tensile properties of laminate A following 35 days exposure in a 50°C, 96% R.H. environment.

The 0.25% secant modulus of the unspiked laminates fell very drastically, to about 39% of the value for the dry material, by the

time moisture levels approached 1.5%. There was no additional large deterioration in modulus, strength or elongation as a consequence of a high tensile stress being applied during the hot, wet exposure. The ultimate failure stress fell to a lesser extent as a result of moisture, and the strain at failure was only slightly decreased. Applying a thermal spike produced a small further fall in modulus and failure stress which could have been a result of the increased moisture content recorded for both loaded and unloaded samples.

TABLE 2
Tensile properties of $[(\pm 45^\circ)_4]_S$ coupons of laminate A tested at 130°C

STRESS DURING EXPOSURE (MPa)	SAMPLE SIZE	No. of SPIKES	MOISTURE CONTENT (%)	U.T.S. (MPa)	0.25 % SECANT MODULUS (GPa)	STRAIN to FAILURE (%)
0	4	0	0	217±5	13.4±.2	14.4±1
0	3	0	1.55	164±3	5.2±.2	13.6±.5
0	3	1**	1.80	156±6	4.3±.2	13.7±1
150	2	0	1.79	167±2	4.7±.1	13.5±.2
150	2	1**	1.96	155±1	4.6±.1	13.3±.1

** Jigs and runners thermally spiked after 20 days and returned for further 15 days in 50°C , 96% R.H. environment.

Table 3 shows the effects of 44 weekly spikes on the mechanical properties of laminates A, B and C. In the case of laminate B, the test temperature was 90°C because its maximum recommended operating temperature was of that order.

TABLE 3
The tensile properties of $[(\pm 45^\circ)_4]_S$ coupons of A, B and C following a series of thermal spikes.

MATERIAL (test temp. $^\circ\text{C}$)	MOISTURE CONTENT (% w/w)	No. of TESTS	No. of SPIKES	U.T.S. (MPa)	.25% SECANT MODULUS (GPa)	STRAIN to FAILURE (%)
A (130)	0	4	0	212±4	12.4±.2	12.5±.2
	2.0	4	0	154±4	7.4±1.0	12.6±1.0
	3.7	4	44	128±2	4.3±.7	12.4±.3
B (90)	0	3	0	254±5	13.3±.2	18.0±.6
	1.5	2	0	179±1	10.9±.2	19.1±.7
	2.2	2	44	164±4	9.4±0	18.6±1.1
C (130)	0	3	0	302±11	10.1±1.6	36.5±1.3
	.32	3	0	265±10	10.0±1.6	29.0±1.2
	.45	3	44	268±1.3	9.8±1.8	31.3±3.1

The trend seen in table 3 is the reducing effect of thermal spiking with increasing matrix toughness (c.f. strain to failure which is in the order $C > B > A$). The ultimate tensile stress, (U.T.S.), and the secant modulus of material A undergo further decreases as a result of thermal spiking following saturation. Material B is not affected so badly, and material C shows no noticeable deterioration.

Figure 1 demonstrates that the moisture absorption divided by the equilibrium moisture uptake as a function of square root of time of exposure of the three laminates to $72^{\circ}\text{C}/96\%$ R.H., is very similar for all three materials. The equilibrium moisture uptake values, M_M , were much greater for the epoxy materials and in the order $A > B > C$. The terms α and β in Figure 1 are the same as those discussed by Bonniau and Bunsell [5]. These terms arise because of the fact that at any instant a fraction of the water molecules are physically bound to the matrix, e.g. hydrogen bonded to hydroxyl or ketone groups. α is the probability that a molecule will change from the bound to the free state, and β is the converse. Unexpectedly, the PEEK-based laminate shows the same $\alpha/(\alpha+\beta)$ as the epoxy type A.

Figure 2 shows that the increase in moisture absorption of spiked laminates was in the same order as the M_M values. Those laminates which contained most moisture prior to the spike programme absorbed the most additional moisture during the 44-spike sequence. However, the moisture absorption of spiked laminates was also in reverse order of matrix toughness, which is consistent with the theory that physical damage is induced by spiking and results in further moisture absorption.

The question arises whether physical damage to the matrix occurs (a) at all, (b) only as a result of high tensile stresses, (c) during the heating stage of the spike, when water vaporises, or (d) during the cooling stage of the spike, when the matrix contracts onto a swollen moisture filled free volume, causing local internal stresses.

Table 2 suggests that (b) is unlikely as no effect on mechanical properties is observed after prolonged tensile loading. In order to distinguish between (c) and (d), two specimens of laminate A were left at 135°C long enough for about one third of the moisture to evaporate before cooling took place. Holding at 135°C for 90 minutes during each of eleven spikes resulted in much reduced moisture uptake during subsequent absorption. These samples eventually reached equilibrium values of 2.36% instead of 3.05% for the ones subjected to short

Figure 1. Moisture absorption characteristics for A, B and C exposed to a 72°C, 96% R.H. environment.

Figure 2. Moisture absorption during a series of 44 thermal spikes of A, B and C.

5-minute spikes. There was also less S.E.M. evidence of microcracking. Figures 3(i) to 4(ii) are S.E.M. photomicrographs of laminate A.

Figure 3 (i) Through thickness section of saturated sample of A [x 20]
 (ii) Enlargement [x 2000]
 (Unspiked)

Figure 4 (i) Through thickness section of spiked sample of A [x 20]
 (ii) Enlargement [x 2000]

Figures 3(i) and (ii) show that even without thermal spiking, samples which have reached equilibrium moisture content contain evidence of some very fine cracking in the matrix and a certain amount of debonding. However, comparison with Figure 4(i) and (ii) shows the dramatic effect of thermal spiking. Much larger cracks are present. It should be noted that in Figure 4(i) the cracking is confined to the inner regions of the laminate, and seems to follow ply boundaries. This would be consistent with the cooling part of the cycle causing damage, as the outer plies tend to dry out during the heating and "hold" stages of the spike. The cracks appear to initiate as fibre-resin debonds.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Free volume theory provides a suitable basis for predicting the effect of stress on diffusion coefficients.

2. Applied stress does not produce a significant deterioration in the hygrothermal response of unspiked laminates of type A, within the limits of the experimental parameters used.
3. The extent of damage is a function of the toughness of the matrix, being less for tougher materials, and severe in the case of epoxy A.
4. One of the more damaging stages of the thermal spike is the cooling step. There is probably a maximum moisture content, below which no damage occurs.

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